

DESIGN OF HIGH-SPEED VITERBI DECODER FOR ERROR CORRECTION AND DETECTION IN COMMUNICATION ON ASIC USING FPGA

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ABSTRACT: One common way that communication systems decode convolutional codes is via the Viterbi algorithm. Codes used in cellular, radio relay, satellite communication, and other applications are decoded using this technique. The method has also found use in storage devices and automated voice recognition. Architectures based on low-complexity, low-latency Viterbi decoders are given in this study with efficient error detection techniques. The suggested systems' strength is in their adaptability; they include criteria for reliability, overhead tolerance, and performance degradation restrictions into their structures. Our work also includes three iterations of re-computing using encoded operands, along with signature-based approaches for detecting both temporary and permanent defects. Additional measures are taken to enhance its power efficiency by using the Spurious-Power Suppression Technique (SPST). In order to preserve power, the suggested SPST divides the target designs into two parts: the most important portion (MSP) and the least significant part (LSP). When the MSP is not affecting the calculation results, it is turned off. Also, by asserting the data signals after the data transient period, this work suggests a novel glitch-diminishing method to eliminate

unnecessary switching power. You may use the suggested granular methods according to your dependability goals and your degradation tolerance for performance/implementation metrics.

Keywords: Error Detection, Speech recognition, Most Significant Part, Least Significant Part.

INTRODUCTION

One such maximum likelihood approach for convolutional codes is the Viterbi algorithm. The method finds the most probable route through the trellis by maximising the Hamming distance, which is calculated for each branch in the trellis. By removing the least probable route at each level of transmission, the method minimises the complexity. Choosing the right way This measure is called survivor, while the other pathways that come in are called non-survivors. The best route is chosen at random from among the best pathways if more than one path shares the best statistic. The Viterbi algorithm is designed to end with the highest probability route, and its core function is to choose survivors. Once the trellis nodes have all been labelled and the entering survivors have been identified, the algorithm exits.

BASIC BUILDING BLOCKS OF VITERBI DECODER

A computer that uses the Branch Metric, which is usually based on a table that contains the different bit metrics. The branch metric is computed by adding up the n-bit metrics that are linked to each branch. This process is carried out by the computer. The outcome is then sent to the storage and path metric update component. After the BMC calculates the branch metric, the Path Metric Updating and Storage process calculates the partial path metrics for each trellis mode. The storage unit is updated with the discovered surviving route. The decoder makes regular use of the Add Compare Select Unit. To decode a received sequence of length L, the number of ACS needed is $L*2M$, where M is the entire memory and r is the coding rate. Keeping tabs on the data bits linked to the pathways that have survived, as determined by the path metric updating and storage unit, is the job of the Information Sequence Updating and Storage (ISUS). Once the Track Back Unit has received the whole frame, it is their job to follow the survivors' progress.

EXISTING SYSTEM

For example, cryptographic designs that use concurrent error detection are resistant to defects, whether caused by nature or by malevolent actors. Several sub-components

of the arithmetic unit are only one example of the many hardware designs in diverse disciplines that have included error detection.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

We evaluate goals in terms of performance metrics and reliability while proposing error detection techniques for the modified Viterbi decoder. Proposed methods include signature-based techniques (such as modified self-checking based on two-rail encoding) and variants of re-computing with encoded operands on various architectures inside the modified Viterbi decoder. The Viterbi algorithm uses two different methods for its two distinct kinds of sub-parts. In addition, our designs provide methods for hardware redundancy via detection based on signatures. We use many self-checking variations based on two-rail encoding for the adder components in particular. In order to identify mistakes, the operations are replayed in the suggested dependable scheme for various operands. Typically, operands are applied at the first step. It is possible to provide accurate results by encoding and applying the operands in the recomputed step and then decoding them.

SIGNATURE BASED SCHEME

The ACS is designed to be fast by implementing parallelization of add and compare operations. This results in a 50% decrease in iteration bound latency. That can be accomplished by adding one bit to the channel response and doubling the number of states. Each branch of a complicated trellis must have a parallel route for it to be considered P-level parallel. The comparison operation is not performed for the first $K - 1$ steps, but it is followed by the add operation for the remaining $M - K + 1$ steps, which aids in removing parallelism. The steps of adding and comparing must be carried out in a certain order. In this method, the previous add-compare order is swapped out for compare-add, and the result is a CSA unit. Its speed-optimized version, the pre-computed

CSA (PCSA), is best used with big K and small M values. For both the CSA and PCSA units, we use prediction techniques that are based on signatures [1]. We see that such units are susceptible to stuck-at faults, which may provide erroneous (multi-bit) results (the mistake can also propagate to the circuits ahead of the damaged spot, spreading like a domino effect throughout the system). All the registers in our proposed approach use signatures, which might be single-bit, multiple-bit, interleaved parity, cyclic redundancy check, or similar. Additionally, the adder modules include a modified self-checking adder (MSeCA) that is based on dual-rail encoding.

Fig 1. CSA Signature Based Error Detection Approach

Fig 2. PCSA Signature Based Error Detection Approach

Figures 1 and 2 show that the CSA unit only has one multiplexer, while the PCSA unit originally had two. To compare the results of the two, an XOR gate was used, with the output of the original multiplexer connected to one of the inputs of the OR gate. To identify errors, the input and output registers are enhanced with extra signatures, such as cyclic redundancy check, interleaved parity, or single-bit, multiple-bit, or interleaved parity. To get the error indication flags, you need an OR gate for the units. When an error is identified, the OR gate will raise the

appropriate error indicator flags. For the CSA unit, this is CSA_Error, and for the PCSA unit, it is PCSA_Error. The updated self-checking adder may also be used to implement the adders in both CSA and PCSA designs. To choose the actual sum bits, this variation uses the original carry-in value; to precompute the bits with complemented carry-in values, i.e., 0 and 1, two n-bit full adders based on multiplexers are used. We try out this new adder in the architectures and see how well it works.

IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS

SIMULATION RESULTS

Fig 3 RTL Schematic

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Timing constraint: Default OFFSET OUT AFTER for Clock 'Clock'
Total number of paths / destination ports: 6272 / 32
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Offset:                12.868ns (Levels of Logic = 6)
Source:                OB_0 (FF)
Destination:          YC1<7> (FAD)
Source Clock:         Clock rising

Data Path: OB_0 to YC1<7>

Cell:in->out    fanout    Gate    Net    Delay    Delay    Logical Name (Net Name)
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FD:C->Q        5    0.591  0.776  OB_0 (OB_0)
LUT2:I0->O     1    0.648  0.452  SC/Mxor_30_0_w0<0>21 (M111)
LUT4:I2->O     1    0.648  0.563  EAB/e026 (EAB/e026)
LUT4:I0->O    36    0.648  1.406  EAB/e0206 (e0)
LUT4:I0->O     8    0.648  0.900  SEC/Mmux_YC31211 (SEC/W2)
LUT4:I0->O     1    0.648  0.420  SEC/Mmux_YC35 (YC3_2_OBUF)
OBUF:I->O      1    4.520

Total                12.868ns (8.351ns logic, 4.517ns route)
                    (64.9% logic, 35.1% route)
    
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Fig 4 DESIGN SUMMARY

Device Utilization Summary (estimated values)			
Logic Utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Number of Slices	91	16640	0%
Number of Slice Flip-Flops	112	33280	0%
Number of 4-input LUTs	150	33280	0%
Number of bonded IOBs	69	309	22%
Number of GCLKs	1	24	4%

Fig 5 TIME SUMMARY

Fig 6 ENCODER OUTPUT

Fig 7 BMU OUTPUT

Fig 8 ACS OUTPUT

Fig 9 PCSA OUTPUT

Fig 10 VITERBI OUTPUT

A fault model that takes into account permanent, transient, and single/multiple-bit stuck-at faults was used to evaluate the fault coverage of the suggested designs. You may find both long-term and temporary problems using the suggested error detection strategies.

COMPARISON TABLE:

ARCHITECTURE	AREA(GATE COUNT)	POWER(mW)
CSA_RCA	1179	133.75
PCSA_RCA	777	103.30
CSA_REROSO	686	486.67
PCSA_REROSO	881	515.87
CSA_SPST	726	122.65
PCSA_SPST	360	103.30
CSA_REROSO_SPST	548	472.86
PCSA_REROSO_SPST	680	444.09

CONCLUSION

We have introduced error detection designs for the Viterbi decoder's low-complexity, low-latency CSA and PCSA structures in this study. All of the above methods use signatures and different kinds of fine-tuned re-computing with rotated operands. The suggested CSA and PCSA unit designs provide near-perfect fault coverage (nearly 100%) in the simulation results when using the specified fault model. Further, the results of the FPGA implementation demonstrate that the produced overheads are satisfactory.

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By manipulating the error indicator flags, we may insert defects at various points. The number of faults recognised for single stuck-at faults in RESO and RERO alone has been determined by two simulations.

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